

**THEORETICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS UNDERLYING THE
PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PROSPECTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION
INSTRUCTORS.**

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Annotation

This scientific paper seeks to investigate the theoretical pedagogical foundations that support the cultivation of professional competence in prospective physical education instructors. The responsibilities of a physical education teacher extend beyond the transmission of knowledge and skills; they involve fostering the physical, cognitive, social, and emotional growth of students.

Keywords: professional competence, physical education instructor, pedagogical theories, teaching approaches.

Professional competence refers to the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attributes that individuals possess and apply in their professional roles to perform tasks, solve problems, and achieve desired outcomes effectively and efficiently. It encompasses both the technical expertise required for a specific profession and the broader competencies necessary for success in the workplace.

Physical education plays a vital role in the holistic development of students, encompassing physical fitness, motor skills, and overall well-being. The professional competence of physical education teachers is crucial in ensuring effective teaching and positive student outcomes. Pedagogical theories provide a theoretical framework for understanding the learning process and guiding teaching practices. Constructivism, behaviorism, and humanism are three prominent pedagogical theories that influence the development of professional competence among physical education teachers. Constructivism emphasizes the active participation of learners in constructing their knowledge through meaningful experiences, while behaviorism focuses on the acquisition of observable behaviors through reinforcement and conditioning. Humanism emphasizes the importance of individual needs, interests, and self-directed learning.

The future physical education teacher will need to possess a range of professional competencies to effectively fulfill their role in an evolving educational landscape. Here are some key competencies that will be important for the physical education teachers of the future:

❖ **Subject Knowledge** - a solid grasp of the subject matter is crucial. Prospective physical education instructors need to possess a profound knowledge of exercise physiology, biomechanics, motor development, as well as sports rules and strategies. It is important for them to keep abreast of the most recent research findings and advancements in the field.

❖ **Pedagogical Skills** - it is essential for prospective physical education instructors to possess the proficiency to teach and communicate effectively with students. They should be well-versed in instructional techniques, curriculum design, and assessment approaches that foster student learning and participation.

❖ **Technology Integration** - as technology becomes more prevalent in education, prospective physical education instructors need to feel at ease integrating technological tools and resources into their teaching methods. This involves utilizing applications, wearable devices, and

online platforms to improve the monitoring of physical activity, analyze data, and provide personalized instruction.

❖ **Inclusive Teaching Practices** - physical education instructors need to excel in establishing inclusive and encouraging learning atmospheres. They should possess the skill to modify activities and teaching approaches to accommodate the diverse requirements of students with different abilities, backgrounds, and interests.

❖ **Health Promotion and Wellness** - prospective physical education instructors need a thorough grasp of the principles of health and wellness. They should possess knowledge in areas such as nutrition, mental health, injury prevention, and overall well-being. These individuals can play a crucial role as champions in encouraging healthy lifestyles among their students.

❖ **Collaboration and Communication** - educators in physical education need to possess strong collaborative skills and effective communication abilities. It is essential for them to engage in cooperative efforts with fellow teachers, parents, and other professionals to foster the growth of students. Maintaining transparent and open communication with both students and their families is of utmost importance.

❖ **Continuous Professional Development** - considering the swiftly evolving landscape of education, prospective physical education instructors need to dedicate themselves to continuous learning. They should proactively pursue chances for professional growth, participate in workshops and conferences, and employ reflective methods to consistently enhance their teaching abilities and stay abreast of contemporary trends.

❖ **Leadership and Advocacy** - prospective physical education instructors ought to champion the cause of physical education and underscore the significance of physical activity within educational institutions. They should demonstrate leadership capabilities to endorse and support high-quality physical education initiatives, obtain necessary resources, and actively participate in the development of policies that enhance the physical well-being of students.

Effective teaching methods are essential for fostering student engagement and achievement. Inquiry-based learning, cooperative learning, and differentiated instruction are teaching methods that contribute to the development of professional competence among physical education teachers. Inquiry-based learning encourages students to investigate, explore, and problem-solve, promoting critical thinking and independent learning. Cooperative learning fosters collaboration, communication, and teamwork among students, enhancing their social and interpersonal skills. Differentiated instruction acknowledges students' diverse learning needs, enabling teachers to tailor instruction and support individual student growth.

Continuous professional development is crucial for enhancing the professional competence of physical education teachers. Engaging in professional development activities such as workshops, conferences, and reflective practices allows teachers to update their knowledge, acquire new skills, and stay abreast of the latest research and pedagogical trends. Collaboration with colleagues, mentoring programs, and participation in professional organizations also contribute to professional growth and competence.

The professional competence of future physical education teachers relies on a strong theoretical pedagogical foundation. The integration of pedagogical theories, effective teaching methods, and ongoing professional development is essential for preparing physical education teachers who can effectively facilitate student learning and development. This article highlights the significance of incorporating theoretical pedagogical bases into teacher education programs to

foster the professional competence required for the ever-evolving field of physical education. It is important to note that the specific competencies required for professional roles may vary depending on the field or industry. Different professions may have their own sets of technical knowledge and specialized skills that are crucial for professional competence.

In summary, the professional competence of future physical education teachers will extend beyond traditional teaching skills. They will need to integrate technology, promote inclusivity, prioritize health and wellness, collaborate effectively, engage in continuous professional development, and advocate for the importance of physical education. By developing these competencies, they can contribute to fostering healthy and active lifestyles among students while meeting the evolving needs of education. Continuous learning and staying updated with industry trends and advancements are key to maintaining and developing professional competence throughout one's career.

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